

Action Plan for the Development of Teaching Factory Based on Strategic Priorities

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Abstract:- Efforts to achieve national development goals require harmony and implementation between various sectors of life. Improve regional development, utilizing existing potential, and a concept of local economic development and an appropriate learning approach is needed in terms of learning that can be applied. It is necessary to have research related to the action plan for developing a priority-based Kemuning teaching factory restaurant in the future. This study, which combines exploratory, descriptive, and explicatory exploration, falls under the category of check exploration. This study employs a geek analysis as its method of analysis. The exploration's discussions led to the conclusion that the strategy for building the Kemuning restaurant teaching factory based on strategy precedence produced 22 action plans and ten strategies for building a precedence-based teaching factory strategy. This research's discussion can be used to develop a strategy for building a teaching factory. The development of facilities for business results and teaching factory support needs to be adjusted to the commodities developed and the hierarchy of needs for these facilities.

Keywords:- Action Plan; Teaching Factory; Strategic Priorities; Local Economic Development.

I. INTRODUCTION

Hypertension is one of the diseases caused by an increase in the perpetration of indigenous autonomy has implications for the ability of regions (counties, metropolises) to develop their capacity to turn the product, allocation, and division of colourful coffers into high-quality productions with a competitive advantage, regardless of whether the requests are original, indigenous, public, or even transnational. Regional Economic evolution is the process by which people take being coffers and form cooperation models

to produce new employment openings and stimulate indigenous profitable excrescency and evolution [1]. Any profitable evolution trouble is levelled at adding mortal coffers in tours of the number and manners of jobs accessible to society [1]. mortal coffers are substance possessed by a mortal commodity in the shape of capacities, chops, dynamism, and moxie that can bring effects [2]. Obtaining good results requires quality human resources [3]. One of the ways that can be taken to ameliorate quality mortal coffers is through instruction. Instruction is a conscious trouble to prepare scholars through guidance, tutoring, and training conditioning for their part in the future. In scoring the public evolution pretensions, videlicet the evolution of the entire Indonesian people and the evolution of all Indonesian people, harmony and perpetration are demanded between colorful life spots to apply these evolution pretensions [4]. To ameliorate indigenous evolution, the application of being eventuality, and in tours of literacy that can be applied, a conception of original profitable evolution and teaching factory literacy approaches are demanded [5].

"Teaching factory concept as an approach that combines the learning and working environment from which realistic and relevant learning experiences arise" Relevant learning experiences are provided by the teaching factory concept approach, which combines instruction with a real-world workplace. Three factors led to the discovery of the teaching factory concept: (1) Ordinary learning is not enough, (2) Student benefits are obtained from hands-on practical experience, and (3) Team-based learning experiences involving students, teaching staff and industry participation enrich the educational process and provide tangible benefits for all parties.

Based on the description of the phenomenon above, research is needed on the action plan for developing teaching factory restaurants based on strategic priorities. It is to

improve the economy of the regional community by not letting go of the learning process. A good factory-based teaching process and a resilient and sustainable community economy can be created in the future. Several problems can be formulated, namely the first: what are the internal and external factors that can affect the development of the Kemuning restaurant teaching factory; second: how is the right alternative strategy to be applied to the Kemuning restaurant teaching plant; third: what is the right strategy priority-based action plan that will be applied to the development of the Kemuning restaurant teaching plant.

There have been numerous studies that have examined the precedence of the strategy. still, each region has characteristics related to the conditions for determining the right strategy. In addition, the focus of the problem studied is that it has not been done much by former experimenters related to the action plan for the development of business units grounded on strategic precedence and is nearly related to the development of teaching factories. The donation of each of the exploration journals mentioned earlier is to be material for collecting state of the art, which is related to the collection of propositions and references whether they support or don't support the exploration. Everything is done so that the exploration becomes further solid and can be used as a reference. From state of the art, it can be seen that no bone explicitly discusses the action plan for developing teaching factories in Kemuning eatery grounded on strategic precedence. therefore, it can be concluded that this exploration is fairly new and has not been done much by former experimenters.

II. METHODS

This research belongs to the type of check exploration and is a combination of exploratory, descriptive and explicatory exploration. Exploratory exploration is carried out to gain in- depth information on weighting, standing, and the expression of indispensable strategies synthesized through theoretical and empirical studies before continuing with descriptive exploration. The position of the study was determined designedly at the teaching factory Kemuning eatery POLIJE, which is located in Kemuning Lor Village, Arjasa District, Jember Regency, East Java, and also as a durability of former exploration. The unborn stopgap is to prepare modeling and design development of teaching factory

Kemuning eatery as an Agribusiness/Agroindustry tourism area and integrated sustainable and environmentally friendly marketing. This exploration was conducted from March to December 2022. The population in this study was the director of Kemuning eatery. The slice fashion is carried out with anon-probability system, a intentional slice system grounded on specific considerations, videlicet knowledge, capability, and experience in the field under study. Primary data is collected through direct interviews with eatery directors through valid and dependable questionnaires. Secondary data is sourced from data or information possessed by applicable agencies (both published and unpublished), as well as books, journals, or colorful forms of publication, as stated in the bibliography. The analysis fashion used is the geek analysis system. SWOT analysis is a form of analysis of the internal and external conditions of an association/ society, which will also be used as a base for designing work strategies and programs. The logical tools used in formulating and prioritizing strategies are IFE, EFE, IE, and geek matrices [6]. likewise, the action plan is prepared grounded on the precedence of the teaching factory eatery Kemuning development strategy combined with the being geek conditions in the current conditions.

III. RESULTS

Overview of Jember State Polytechnic is one of the universities in Indonesia that organizes vocational education. Educational programs that lead to the teaching and learning process at a certain level of expertise, skills, and competency standards follow the needs of the job market and stakeholders. They have independence in work and entrepreneurship based on science and technology. Until now, the Polytechnic has had 8 Departments and 22 Study Programs, as well as 8 Academic Support Units, one of which is the Teaching Factory Kemuning restaurant.

A. Internal factor evaluation matrix

This IFE matrix is collected grounded on interviews conducted with eatery directors. Weighting is done by comparing each of the internal factors of the teaching factory to get the factor that takes priority. likewise, the standing is carried out by looking at the factual condition of the teaching factory eventuality to get the main strengths and sins in the teaching factory development area.

TABLE I. IFE MATRIX

No	Internal Factors	Rating	Weight	Score
Strength				
1	Very strategic geographical location	4	0.133	0.533
2	Adequate human resources	4	0.087	0.346
3	Potential age	3	0.095	0.286
4	Education level	3	0.080	0.240
5	Perseverance / Motivation	4	0.115	0.462
6	Extensive marketing aspects	4	0.124	0.497
Weakness				
1	There is no adequate information system in public services	2	0.061	0.122
2	Untargeted government support	2	0.064	0.129
3	Lack of local employment	2	0.051	0.102
4	Lack of business planning and development actions that have the	1	0.132	0.132

	potential for economic value			
5	Poor waste management	2	0.056	0.113
	Total		1.000	2.962

In the IFE matrix over, it can be concluded that the main strength of the teaching factory development is a veritably strategic geographical position with a score of 0.533. Meanwhile, the main weakness of teaching factory development is the lack of planning and business development conduct with implicit profitable value (0.132). The total concerted score for the internal factors of teaching factory development is 2.962, which means that the development of the teaching factory has strengths and sins above the average standard of 2.50.

B. External factor evaluation matrix

This EFE matrix was collected from interviews with several applicable institutions, academic interpreters, and implicit resides. Weighting is done by comparing all external factors of the teaching factory to determine the factors to be prioritized. In addition, the assessment is grounded on the factual response of the implicit development of the training factory to being or anticipated openings and pitfalls.

TABLE II. EFE MATRIX

No	External Factors	Rating	Weight	Score
Opportunity				
1	Teaching factory development prospects	4	0.209	0.836
2	Supporting resources	4	0.101	0.404
3	Rich in superior products	3	0.094	0.282
4	There are still vast market opportunities	4	0.129	0.516
5	Have partner cooperation	3	0.086	0.259
Threat				
1	Low interest in community business development	1	0.206	0.206
2	Societal stigma about the importance of education	2	0.054	0.109
3	Many unemployed at the age of the labor force	2	0.059	0.118
4	Waste and waste have not been managed properly	2	0.061	0.123
	Total		1.00	2.853

In the EFE matrix over, it can be concluded that the main occasion factor for the development of a teaching factory is the prospect of developing a teaching factory with a score of 0.836. Meanwhile, the main trouble that the development of teaching factories has watched out for is the low public interest in business development, with a score of

0.206. The total concerted score for external factors for teaching factory development is 2.853, which means that the development of teaching factory in the face of openings and pitfalls can be said to be good because it has exceeded the average standard of 2.50.

C. Internal-external matrix

Fig. 1. SWOT Matrix

Fig. 2. IE Matrix

TABLE III. SWOT ANALYSIS

	Strength (S)	Weakness (W)
	1. Very strategic geographical location 2. Adequate human resources 3. Potential age 4. Education Level 5. Perseverance / Motivation 6. Extensive marketing aspects	1. There's no acceptable information system in public services 2. Untargeted government support 3. Lack of local employment 4. Lack of business planning and development actions that have the potential for economic value 5. Poor waste management
Opportunity (O)	SO	WO
Teaching factory development prospects Supporting resources Rich in superior products There are still vast market opportunities Have partner cooperation	Facilitating teaching factory actors Kemuning restaurant based on strategic priorities with production machines that are used communally (S2, S3, O1, O2) Providing a place for the use of production machines for Kemuning restaurant teaching factory actors (S1, S2, O3) Providing media for cooperation with private parties (S6, O4, O5) Increasing the share of the online culinary market abroad (S1, S5, S6, O3, O4, O5)	Increase online product marketing and promotion activities through cooperation with government parties (W2, W4, O1, O5) Increasing marketing and promotional activities for teaching factory Kemuning restaurant products through cooperation with the restaurant community or teaching factory (W4, O2, O3, O4, O5)
Threat (T)	ST	WT
Low interest in community business development Societal stigma about the importance of education Many unemployed at the age of the labor force Waste and waste have not been managed properly	Increasing the number of experts in the field of teaching factory Kemuning restaurant (S2, S6, T1, T3) Increase marketing financing and promotion of Kemuning restaurant teaching factory products (S6, T1)	Increase thematic training activities related to the development of the Kemuning restaurant teaching factory based on strategy priorities (W3, W5, T2, T3, T4) Building linkage with creative industries of other subsectors to support marketing and promotional activities of Teaching Factory Kemuning restaurant products (W1, W4, T1)

According to David [7] IE (Internal External) matrix positions the colorful divisions of an association in a nine-cell view. Each division within an association must produce an IFE Matrix and an EFE Matrix concerning the association. The IE matrix is grounded on two crucial confines the total IFE weight score on the x-axis and the total EFE weight score on the y-axis. The total weight score attained from similar divisions allows the arrangement of the IE Matrix at the enterprise position. On the x-axis of the IE Matrix, a total IFE weight score of 1.0 to 1.99 indicates a weak internal position; a score of 2.0 to 2.99 is considered moderate, and a score of 3.0 to 4.0 is strong. also, on the y-axis, the total EFE weight

score of 1.0-1.99 is looked down upon; a score of 2.0-2.99 is considered moderate, and a score of 3.0-4.0 is high. The IE matrix can identify nine enterprise strategy cells, but the nine cells can be grouped into three main strategies [7].

Based on the discussion of the factors of strengths, sins, openings, and pitfalls over, it can be concluded that the value of IFE and EFE can be concluded to determine the strategy for developing a teaching factory at Kemuning restaurant State Polytechnic of Jember. thus, the grand strategy matrix can be determined through the geek analysis quadrant in the IFE computation of 1.48 (x-axis) and the EFE computation of

1.43 (y- axis). As for the computation results of IFE and EFE, it's known that the development of the teaching factory is in quadrant 1. In this case, it shows that the development of the teaching factory has relatively good strength and has a nicely good occasion. The total weighting result of the IFE matrix is 2.962, and the EFE matrix is 2.853. Also, the result is counterplotted into the IE matrix, where the x-axis comes from the total value of the IFE matrix and the y- axis comes from the total value of the EFE matrix. So that the IE matrix over can be concluded that the position of teaching factory development is in cell V, the divisions included in cell V can be adequately handled through a strategy of maintaining and maintaining (hold and maintain). Strategies that can be used are request penetration, request development, and product development. request penetration and product development are the two most extensively used strategies.

D. Development strategy of Teaching Factory Kemuning restaurant State Polytechnic of Jember

In realizing the vision and mission of the Kemuning restaurant teaching factory, the development strategy includes:

- It increases product distribution through cooperation with companies providing online delivery order services.
- Increase promotions that can expand the share of the online culinary market abroad.
- Increase marketing activities and product promotion online through cooperation with the government.
- Increase marketing activities and promotion of products of the online culinary creative industry through cooperation with the online culinary community.
- Build linkages with other subsectors of creative industries to support marketing and promotional activities for online culinary products.
- Increase marketing financing and promotion of products in the online culinary creative industry.
- Increase marketing financing and promotion of products in the online culinary creative industry

E. Action plan for the development of Teaching Factory Kemuning restaurant State Polytechnic of Jember

The action plan is prepared based on the Kemuning restaurant teaching factory strategy combined with the existing SWOT conditions in the current conditions. The following is the action plan for the Kemuning restaurant teaching factory at the State Polytechnic of Jember.

- Register online culinary creative industry products on all delivery order applications at the State Polytechnic of Jember.
- Cooperate with delivery order services to get special prices in online culinary product distribution activities.
- Increase the intensity of marketing and product promotion on all social media and e-commerce platforms.
- Increase the use of optimization services for promotional activities through Search Engine Optimization, Google AdWords, Facebook Ads, and Market Place.
- Collaborate with online media partners and popular journalistic media to expand product promotion networks on social media.

- Conduct marketing and promotion activities for online culinary creative industry products through social media and official government-owned websites.
- Introduce online culinary creative industry products to consumers through promotions carried out by online culinary communities and online culinary promotion accounts on social media.
- Hold gatherings, sharing, and product promotion events with the online culinary community at the Jember Art Center.
- Collaborate with the creative industries of the graphic design subsector to create product logos, packaging designs, and advertising designs for promotion.
- Collaborate with the creative industry of the games subsector to create online culinary-themed games as a promotional medium.
- Cooperation with the online culinary community to hold exhibition events or bazaars.
- Cooperate with online applications to advertise culinary games.
- Cooperation with private companies to obtain financing for marketing and product promotion activities.
- Conduct training on marketing and promotion systems through social media and e-commerce through cooperation with academics.
- Cooperate with experts as trainers in online marketing and promotional development training activities.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the discussion in the study, it can be concluded that the strategy for developing a Kemuning restaurant teaching factory based on priority strategies includes: Facilitating Kemuning restaurant teaching factory actors based on strategic priorities with production machines used communally; Providing a place for the use of production machines for Kemuning restaurant teaching factory actors; Providing media for cooperation with private parties; Increase the number of experts in the field of teaching factory Kemuning restaurant; Increase thematic training activities related to the development of Kemuning restaurant teaching factory based on strategy priorities; Increase the share of the online culinary market to abroad; Increase online product marketing and promotion activities through cooperation with the government; Increase marketing and promotional activities of Kemuning restaurant teaching factory products through cooperation with the restaurant community or teaching factory; Build linkage with other subsector creative industries to support marketing and promotional activities of Kemuning restaurant teaching factory products; and increase marketing financing and promotion of teaching factory Kemuning restaurant products. Of the ten strategies analyzed using SWOT analysis and produced 22 action plans to develop a priority-based teaching factory strategy in Kemuning restaurant, Kemuning Lor Village, Arjasa District, Jember Regency, East Java.

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